

An early report on signals from the SSI AHRC Survey on Software/Digital requirements

Author: Chit (Philip) Chan, as part of the UCL Masters Programme in Digital Humanities

Acknowledgement: Shoaib Sufi, supervisor, SSI Community Lead

1. Introduction

Analysing qualitative responses with computational methods remains as a challenging task. The common solution to address this issue is to apply thematic analysis on the responses and cluster themes and identify the key information from different texts. The thematic analysis was conducted based on the sample of responses on three qualitative questions from fifty-six respondents in mid June 2021 from a survey to the [AHRC community on software/digital requirements](#).

These three questions are:

- (1) What do you use research software for?
- (2) Why do you use the research software that you do?
- (3) How could better software practices improve your area or field of work?

The thematic analysis of these three questions is reported under the following three sections. Each section consists of a table clustering topics in the responses to a particular question based on the main author's interpretation with checking from the second author. In the last section, the report will conclude with a holistic understanding derived from the different clusters.

2. Thematic analysis on "What do you use research software for?"

In order to have a better understanding of this question within the context of AHRC Survey, the juxtaposition between this question and the next question (ie. Why do you use the research software that you do?) is beneficial. For this question, respondents are inclined to state their opinions on what research software they use as a tool for their own research field. For the next question, respondents are inclined to give their personal reasons as to their software choices. Therefore the thematic analysis of this question focuses on "tasks".

As a result, a total of 48 tasks were mentioned in the survey. However, it is difficult to cluster these 48 tasks as the overall purpose between these tasks vary greatly. To unify these

themes into clusters with a similar overall purpose, the Northeastern University's data project life cycle was used as a categorisation framework. (Northeastern University, 2020)

The following distribution was thus identified:

- Ten tasks in the data phase
- Nine tasks in the analysis phase
- Three tasks in the visualisation phase
- Two tasks in the hypothesis phase

It is evident from the text that respondents use research software to perform a lot more different tasks (e.g. processes and techniques) in the data phase, analysis phase, visualisation phase and hypothesis phase of their data projects. The distribution mirrors the fact that researchers need to perform more tasks during the data phase and analysis phase. However, it is also worth noticing from Table (a) that certain analytical processes also encompass the visualisation step. (eg. Network analysis requires visualisation to conclude as a result or use the visualisation as a reference for further refinement of analysis tasks. In reality, visualisation tasks occur more than three times, as they are implicitly part of analysis tasks such as network analysis, text analysis, spatial analysis and so forth.

When we look at the data from a macro-perspective, we could identify how the number of tasks vary among different phases of the data project. However, if we look at the data from a micro-perspective, we could identify which tasks have a relatively high frequency, so we can understand which tasks respondents find "software-demanding". Let us divert our attention to the top four most frequently mentioned tasks in Table a, we could see that:

- Data analysis was called fourteen times
- Data processing was called thirteen times
- Data cleaning was called eleven times
- Text analysis was called ten times

(1) It is interesting to note that although the term "data analysis" occurred fourteen times in the respondents' answers to this question. This term has a high level of ambiguity as respondents failed to mention exactly which digital methods they use to analyse their data in their projects.

"Data analysis / data cleaning / visualisation / NER" - Respondent 4

"Data analysis, building websites, project management" - Respondent 5

"Data cleaning, data analysis, data visualisation, automation of simple tasks"-Respondent 13

(2) On the other hand, we see that the "Data processing" and "Data cleaning" tasks are specified or ambiguously stated.

“Access data and process data” - Respondent 6

“Import, integration, analysis, curation, computation, validation, visualisation, publishing of research data” - Respondent 12

*“Data cleaning, data analysis (“methods” I’m applying to a research problem)”
- Respondent 16*

“Data management / collection; data cleaning; descriptive statistics; mapping and spatial analysis; publishing online collections” - Repondent 33

Linking this to the previous paragraph, it is clear to us that respondents use research software to perform different types of work in the data phase of their project, the high frequencies of “data processing” and “data cleaning” signify that the use of research software to perform these two tasks is very common.

(3) The high occurrence of the text analysis process highlights a characteristic of the survey’s target group. AHRC focused researchers engage in “text analysis” on their corpus or research material.

“Analysing large data sets (Pandas); text comparison (automated collation); transforming TEI conformant XML document to HTML” - Respondent 2

“Social network analysis, text mining, visualisation” -Respondent 3

To conclude the writer’s comments on this question, this report reveals the following findings to readers:

- (1) Research tools often used for variety of tasks in the data phase, analysis phase and visualisation phase in respondent’s project
- (2) To carry out data processing and data cleaning tasks, respondents rely heavily on research softwares
- (3) Text analysis has the highest frequency recall compared to all other digital methods, this signifies a big group of our respondents are interested in studying the linguistic part of the humanities using computational methods..

3. Thematic analysis on “Why do you use the research software that you do?”

This thematic analysis aims to understand why the users use the research tool that they used. Once the thematic analysis is completed the themes are then clustered into broader categories.

In our first cluster, we look at the topics surrounding the theme “Accessibility of the research tool”. The meaning of “accessibility” in software requirements often refers to two different meanings. Accessibility in software requirements could mean “How easy it is for users with disabilities to use the software? ” or “To what extent is the software being available for every

user?”. Interestingly, there are not many respondents stating the software is helping their disabilities. Hence, the term “accessibility” is referring to the latter definition. From the twenty topics mentioned in the “themes and clusters” document, there are two topics which are related to the theme of accessibility, which are FOSS (Free and open source software) and accessible through institutional channels. A total of twenty people found that FOSS is one of their reasons for using the research tool, only one person within those twenty people found free and open source is not his/her preference, but his/her collaborator’s preference. Beside the research tool being FOSS. A total number of six people found the research tool is accessible via institutional platforms. Those six people also previously commented about the FOSS features of the research tools.

In our second cluster, we will be looking at the topics under the theme of “Community”. A total number of six topics have been recorded under this cluster, which are: (i) Community standards, (ii) Community vibrancy, (iii) Collaboration, (iv) Sense of belonging, (v) teaching, and (vi) learning. For (i), a total of seventeen people believe community standards are their primary reason, in which twelve of them choose to use the app to comply with the academic standards, meanwhile eight people believe to use the tool to construct community standards, which within these twelve people, three people believe on both points. For (ii), a total number eleven people agree that the technical support for the research tool is widely available from the online community. For (iii), a total number of seven people think that they use the research tool for the collaborative purpose. For (iv), (v), (vi), a handful few who used the research tools for conforming to their sense of belongings, teaching and learning.

In the last cluster, we will be looking at the topic of the “functionalities and features” of the research software. A total number of seven sub-themes have been recorded under this topic, which are: (i) Flexibility, (ii) Simplicity, (iii) Power, (iv) stability, (v) compatibility), (vi) reproducibility, (vii) familiarity. For flexibility, stability, familiarity, we have captured 2, 1, 2 people respectively. However, it does not mean these three features are not important to users, we require more information to make any further acknowledgment. On the other hand, four people or more have commented that simplicity, power, compatibility, reproducibility are the important features or functionalities for the research tool.

To conclude this section, this report reveal the following findings to readers:

- (1) When respondents use a particular software for the purpose of software’s accessibility, it is likely that the software is considered because the software is free and open source.
- (2) When respondents use a particular software for the purpose of “community”, they are likely to be referring to setting or complying to the community standards. It is also worth taking into account that some people use particular software because its community vibrancy could offer help to users.
- (3) When respondents use software for its particular feature, respondents chose the software for the software’s simplicity, efficiency, compatibility and reproducibility.

4. Thematic analysis on “How could better software practices improve your area or field of work?”

This section focuses on the thematic analysis on respondents' responses on the question, "How could better software practices and solutions improve your area or field of work". This question mainly focuses on what respondents believe that could improve their software practices by alternating or improving certain existing features of the software. Hence, the writer believes the main theme this thematic analysis should be identifying is "suggestions".

As a result, the writer has found a total number of eighteen themes within our responses. In order to find the representative answer among similar answers, these eighteen themes were subsequently categorised to four clusters of:

- (1) Documentation
- (2) Training
- (3) Features and function
- (4) Community

(For further details please refer to Table c)

According to the Documentation Cluster Table, there is a total number of five respondents believe easier documentation for the tutorial purpose will benefit their software practices. Four within these five respondents think these tutorial documentation should be more elaborative, and three within these five respondents think these tutorial documentation should have examples or case studies attached. To extract the key information from this cluster, the writer believes an easy, detailed tutorial documentation with examples will be beneficial for respondents' better software practices.

From the Training Cluster Table, a total number of ten respondents believe training will be useful for better software conduct. There are eight respondents who believe software training given to researchers should be more practical. Additionally, five respondents think the training is not frequent and easy enough to optimise their software understanding. One within these five respondents also think Free and Open Source software should also give frequent and easy training to users. An outlier Respondent 19 is a research software engineer, this engineer thinks more software testing training should be given, as it benefits their software maintenance routine. The key information we can extract from this cluster is that respondents find regular, easy and practical software training will lead respondents to better software practices and their productivity could increase from software training.

From the Features and function Clusters Table, relatively high frequencies occurred in the following themes. (a) Softwares should develop reusable functions; (b) software should be more interoperative; (c) software should encompass collaboration features; (d) software should be more efficient. From these four themes, the author sees there is a high demand for softwares to be efficient, collaborative and interoperative, developing reusable functions should be software's top priority. On the other hand, a few respondents think the software that they use should improve their interface design, hence a more intuitive outlook should make the software usable, and allowing screen reading makes the software more accessible.

For the Community Cluster Table, a small group of respondents believe more feedback should be circulating within the research software community. Additionally, they also think the software support team should be more helpful by understanding users' demands and sharing more informative and compatible documents about the software.

To conclude this thematic analysis, the most representative suggestions are summarised as follow:

- (1) Software should provide easier, detailed tutorial documentation with examples to users.
- (2) Users will gain higher productivity if regular easy and practical software training is provided.
- (3) The three features that software needs to enhance are interoperative, collaborative and efficient. In the meantime, it is suggested by users that more intuitive design on interface and allowing screen reading will enhance the software usability and accessibility.
- (4) For better software practice, some users believe an active vibrant research software community stands on a crucial position. On the other hand, some respondents believe help should be given by the research support team.

5. Conclusion: a general review on software requirement

To conclude this report, by merging the key information we gathered in the previous three sections, new information in understanding our respondents is generated.

It is evident that, due to research software's simplicity and efficiency, our respondents rely heavily on research software when they are dealing with data processing and data cleaning. However, a vast majority of our respondents think their research software is not simple and efficient enough. Therefore, to supplement these two insufficiencies, internal support from software could be given in either providing easier and detailed tutorial documentation or providing regular, easy practical training to users. However, some respondents believe a high vibrancy in the research software community could enhance one's efficiency in dealing with data. Yet, a few of our respondents think that improving software's usability (improve interface) and accessibility (enable screen reading) could improve the software's simplicity and efficiency.

Looking from the other side of the software's accessibility, more than one third of our respondents declared that they use the research software that they use because they are free and open source. As the software is free to everyone, it is assumable that the free and open source feature should enable more collaborative projects. However, our survey showed a contradictory point that the software that they use lacks the intuitive interface design and it stops researchers from collaborating with each other. Additionally, our respondents have frequently commented that their software is lacking compatibility and their output could not be shared on similar research softwares as the output is not interoperable.

Last but not least, some of our respondents believe the software that they use is lacking in reusable functions. From section 2, we discovered research software is often used to carry out a variety of tasks in the data, analysis and visualisation phases of their project. Hence, reusable functions should be built on the repetitive tasks users conduct during these three phases.

Bibliography:

1. AHRC (2021), 'Survey of digital/software requirements for the AHRC research community', available at:
<https://www.software.ac.uk/news/survey-digitalsoftware-requirements-ahrc-research-community>
2. Northeastern University (2020), 'How do I start a data project: Understanding a project lifecycle', available at:
<https://www.northeastern.edu/graduate/blog/data-analysis-project-lifecycle/>

6. Cluster Tables

(a) Cluster table of section 2

Stage	Process or Technique	Steps	Respondent ids
Hypothesis	Application Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● enhance UX	9, 28, 41, (3)
	Enhance applicant performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● enhance UX	9, 28, 38, 41, (4)
Data	Data Processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Data extraction● Data Structuring● Data Import● Data Validation● Data integration● Data Model Teting● Data curation● Data visualisation	6, 11, 12, 18, 21, 24, 25, 21, 33, 39, 49, 52, 54, (13)

	Data Cleaning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data extraction • Data Structuring • Data Import • Data Validation 	4, 9, 13, 16, 21, 24, 25, 28, 33, 49, 51, (11)
	Manuscript Transcription	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical edition • Keyword identification • Language concordance • Creation archaeological interpretation • Evaluation archaeological interpretation • Data validation • Data visualisation 	9, 10, 20, 23, 42, 43, (6)
	Ancient text lemmatisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keyword identification • Language concordance 	9, 43, (2)
	Ancient text translation to modern language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keyword identification • Language concordance 	9, 23, 42, 43 (4)
	Data Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data integration • datasets • Data Model Teting • Data curation • Data visualisation 	11, 28, 41, 44, 55, (5)

	Data Workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data extraction • Data Structuring • Data Import • Data Validation • Data integration 	11, 41, (2)
	Archiving		21, 48, 51, (3)
	Simulation Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prediction model • Data validation • Reference management 	11, 44, 53, (3)
	Modelling historic urban transformation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation archaeological interpretation • Evaluation archaeological interpretation 	44, 55, (2)
Analysis	NLP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text lemmatisation • NER 	1, 2, 3, 4, 18 (5)
	Text Analysis		1, 2, 3, 14, 15, 18, 28, 36, 52, 54 (10)
	Network Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data structuring • Data model tesing • Data visualisation 	1, 3, 15, 27, 28, 21, 36 (7)
	Data Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data cleaning • Data visualisation 	2, 4, 5, 12, 13, 16, 24, 25, 27, 35, 38, 40, 51, 56 (14)

	Qualitative Data Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data cleaning • Data visualisation 	8, 10, 29, 36, 55 (5)
	Statistical Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data cleaning • Data Visualisation 	2, 7, 27, 28, 21, 33, 55 (7)
	Spatial Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data visualisation 	33, 44, 53 (3)
	Corpus Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Archive • Data Dissemination 	14, 48, 52 (3)
	Thematic Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Visualisation 	8, 10, 36, 55 (4)
Visualisation	TEI XML Transformation (XSLT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data visualisation 	2, 7 (2)
	Image post-processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data visualisation 	40 (1)
	3D processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data visualisation 	49 (1)

(b) Cluster table of section 3

Cluster name	Topic	Meanings	Number
The accessibility to use the research tool	1. FOSS (Total 20)	(1a) The software is free and open source	(1a) 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 19, 28, 29, 36, 41, 43, 48, 52, 53, 55 (Total 20)
		(1b) Collaborator's preference as the research tool is accessible and free	(1b) 9 (Total 1)
	2. Accessible via institution (Total 6)	(2a) Accessible via institution licence	(2a) 2, 8, 10, 36, 41, 55 (Total 6)

Cluster name	Topic	Meanings	Number
Use research tool for the sake of "Community"	1. Community Standards (Total 17)	(1a) To reach community/ institutional standards	2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 15, 18, 19, 28, 43, 51, 53 (Total 12)
		(1b) Construct domain specific standards	3, 12, 13, 19, 20, 49, 51, 56 (Total 8)
	2. Community Vibrancy (Total 11)	(2a) Community support is widely available	3, 6, 13, 15, 23, 27, 29, 41, 44, 51, 56 (Total 11)
	3. Collaboration (Total 7)	(3a) Project collaboration with others	6, 12, 18, 20, 39, 49, 54 (Total 7)
	4. Sense of belonging (Total 2)	(4a) The research tools are used either because the tools are promoted by their institution or invented by their institution	2, 8 (Total 2)
	5. Teaching (Total 2)	(5a) The research tools are used for	18, 27 (Total 2)

		teaching	
	6. Learning (Total 2)	(6a) The research tools are used for learning	18, 24 (Total 2)

Cluster name	Topic	Meanings	Number
The functionality features that drew DH scholars to use DH research tools	Flexibility (total 2)	(1a) The research tool is flexible	29, 35 (total 2)
	Simplicity (total 6)	(2a) The tool is ease of use	3, 9, 51 (total 3)
		(2b) Contain all functions one needs	11, 23, 56 (total 3)
	Powerful (total 5)	(3a) Contain all function one needs	11, 29, 44 (total 3)
		(3b) Able to deal with mass data	24, 48 (total 2)
	Stability (total 1)	(4a) Making sure the tool is stable for personal and collaborative use	12 (total 1)
	Compatibility (total 5)	(5a) Compatible with their own stack (interoperability)	12, 21, 36, 49, 53 (total 5)
		(5b) Domain specific compatibility requirement	21, 49 (total 2)
	Reproducibility (total 4)	(6a) With written codes, applying new variables, making the research tool more reproducible.	13, 27, 53, 54 (total 4)
	Familiarity (total 2)	(7a) Changed to some research tool as it is familiar to how they used to code before	31, 36 (total 2)

(c) Cluster table on Section 4

Cluster name	Topics	meanings	Number
Documentation	Documentation for tutorial	Easier documentation for tutorial purposes	2, 7, 15, 29, 56 (5)
		Tutorial Documentation with example data	7, 29,56 (3)
		Elaborative tutorial documentation	2, 7, 15,56 (4)

Cluster name	Topics	Meanings	Number
Training	Practical training	respondents request more practical trainings	4, 10, 11, 13, 27, 30, 35, 44 (8)
	Make training regular and easier	respondents want trainings to be easier and regular	5, 11,27, 30, 35 (5)
	More training on open source softwares	respondents want the trainings to be on open source software	5 (1)
	More software testing training for software developers	respondents as software developers want more software testing training	19 (1)

Cluster name	Topics	Meanings	Number
Features and functions	Higher level of customisation in research software		8 (1)
	Higher efficiency by using more efficient workaround solutions		1, 16, 38 (3)
	Make research tools more intuitive		23, 52 (2)
	Make research tools more collaborative		25, 54, 55 (3)
	Make research tools more interoperative		28, 36, 39, 49 (4)
	Develop reusable functions		12, 21, 29, 51, 53 (5)
	Develop functions in structuring and extracting information		18, (1)
	Develop screen reading functions for the research tool		37 (1)
	Use more non-proprietary functions		42 (1)